

ANTI MONOTONIC P-FUZZY G – DISTRIBUTIVE LATTICES

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Abstract:

The main goal of this paper is to study the finite groups whose lattices of fuzzy G-modular are distributive. We obtain a characterization of these lattices which is similar to a well known result of lattice theory.

Key Words: Fuzzy Lattices, Level Set, G-Modular, Anti P-Fuzzy G-Modular Lattices, Fuzzy Filter, Fuzzy Ideal & Lattice Homomorphism.

Introduction:

The theory of fuzzy sets which was introduced by L. A. Zadeh [14] is applied to many mathematical branches. Rosenfeld [13] inspired the fuzzification of algebraic structures and introduced the notion of fuzzy sub groups. P. Das [7] characterized fuzzy sub groups by their level sub groups. In [10] Liu applied the concept of fuzzy sets to the theory of rings and introduced and examined the notion of a fuzzy ideal of a ring. The study of fuzzy sub module was introduced by Pan and Golan in [7]. Also Pan [12] studied the fuzzy finitely generated modules and fuzzy quotient modules. The formation of a lattice of sub modules of a module is well known features in classical algebra. However the same has not been explored in fuzzy setting. In order to initiate such studies the concept of fuzzy sub-module generated by an arbitrary fuzzy set is formulate in this note. Using this concept S.K. Bambri and Pratibakumar [5] introduced Lattice of fuzzy sub modules and established an embedding of the lattice of all sub module of a module M into the lattice of fuzzy sub module.

Q. Zhang and Meng [15] considered the sub property to be an assumption and established the more general result that “the lattice $I_t(R)$ of all fuzzy ideals of a ring R with the same tip “t” is modular. On the other hand in [11] the authors have arrived at the false result that the lattice $I(R)$ is distributive. In fact the lattice $I(R)$ of ideals of a ring R is not distributive and has an obvious embedding in $I(R)$. The corrected result has already appeared in several papers [9, 15]. I Jahan in [11], by constructing and employing the technique of strong level subsets, he proved that the lattice $I(R)$ of all ideals of a ring R is modular. This proof of the modularity of $I(R)$ is different from the Ajmal’s proof of modularity of the lattice of fuzzy normal sub groups of group appeared in [1]. K.C.Gupta and S. Roy in introduce the indirect proof of the above result that the modularity of the quasi Hamiltonians fuzzy sub groups. Hence N. Ajmal and K.V. Thomas in [2] initiated a discussion on the aspect of modularity of the set of fuzzy normal sub groups. A special class of fuzzy normal sub groups of group has been shown to constitute a modular sub lattice of its fuzzy sub group lattice. They first established that the sub lattice (G) is modular. Moreover using the same technique in [3], they demonstrate that whenever the set (G) of all fuzzy quasi normal sub groups of a given group forms a lattice, the lattice is modular. B. Yuan and Wu. Wangning in [4], introduced fuzzy ideals on a distributive lattice. In this paper, we study the characterization of fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice such as ring sums, lattice homomorphism and upper level sets.

Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1:

A non empty set L together with two binary operations \vee and \wedge on L is called a lattice if it satisfies the following identities.

$$\begin{aligned} L1: & \quad x \vee y \approx y \vee x, x \wedge y \approx y \wedge x \\ L2 & \quad x \vee (y \vee z) \approx (x \vee y) \vee z, x \wedge (y \wedge z) \approx (x \wedge y) \wedge z \\ L3 & \quad x \vee x \approx x, x \wedge x \approx x \\ L4 & \quad x \approx x \vee (x \wedge y), x \approx x \wedge (x \vee y). \end{aligned}$$

The operation \wedge is called meet and the operation \vee is called join. Let L be the set of proposition and let \vee denote the connective “or” and \wedge denote the connective “and”. Then L1 to L4 are well known properties from propositional logic.

Definition 2.2:

A distributive lattice is a lattice which satisfies either of the distributive laws. D1. $x \wedge (y \vee z) \approx (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$, D2 $x \vee (y \wedge z) \approx (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z)$. One can see a lattice L satisfies D1 if and only if satisfies D2.

Definition 2.3:

Let G be a group and L be a vector distributive lattice then L is called G- modular if for a $\in G$ and $l \in L$, there exist a product $a \cdot l \in L$ satisfies the following axioms.

- (i) $e \cdot l = l$, for all $l \in L$

- (ii) $(a \cdot h) \cdot l = a \cdot (h \cdot l)$
- (iii) $a \cdot (k_1 \cdot m_1 + k_2 \cdot m_2) = k_1 \cdot (a \cdot m_1) + k_2 \cdot (a \cdot m_2)$ for all $k_1, k_2 \in K$ and $m_1, m_2 \in M$.

Definition 2.4:

A mapping $\mu: X \times P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ where X is an arbitrary non-empty set and is called a P-fuzzy set in X .

Definition 2.5:

Let X be a P-fuzzy set and $\mu: X \times P \rightarrow G$ be a lattice ordered group of X . Then μ is called P-fuzzy lattice ordered group (PFLG) if

- (i) $\mu(x + y, p) \geq \min\{\mu(x, p), \mu(y, p)\}$
- (ii) $\mu(-x, p) \geq \mu(x, p)$
- (iii) $\mu(0, p) = 1$, for all $x, y \in G$.

Definition 2.6:

Let μ be a P-fuzzy lattice ordered group of G and $\mu: X \times P \rightarrow G$. Then μ is called P-fuzzy lattice if

- (i) $\mu(x + y, p) \geq \min\{\mu(x, p), \mu(y, p)\}$
- (ii) $\mu(-x, p) \geq \mu(x, p)$
- (iii) $\mu(x \vee y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$
- (iv) $\mu(x \wedge y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in G$.

Definition 2.7:

Let X be any group and L be a vector distributive lattice extended real valued functions on X . If μ is called a anti P-fuzzy G-modular lattice on L then it satisfies the following conditions.

- (i) $\mu(ax + by, p) \leq \max\{\mu(x, p), \mu(y, p)\}$
- (ii) $\mu(gx, p) \leq \mu(x, p)$
- (iii) $\mu(x \vee y)_p \wedge (x \wedge y)_p \leq \max\{\mu(x, p), \mu(y, p)\}$, for all $x, y \in L$.

Definition 2.8:

A P-fuzzy sub set μ is called monotonic if $\mu(x, p) \leq \mu(y, p)$ whenever $x \leq y$

Definition 2.9:

Let μ be any P-fuzzy sub set of X . Then the set $\mu_t = \{x \in X / (\mu(x, p) \geq t, t \in [0, 1])\}$ is called a level sub set of μ .

Definition 2.10:

- (i) A monotonic fuzzy G-modular lattice is called a fuzzy filter of L .
- (ii) A anti-monotonic fuzzy G-modular lattice is called a fuzzy ideal of L .
- (iii) A P-fuzzy sub set μ is called a P-fuzzy filter if and only if $\mu(x \wedge y)_p = \mu(x, p) \wedge \mu(y, p)$, for all $x, y \in L$.
- (iv) A P-fuzzy subset μ is called a Q-fuzzy ideal if and only if $(\mu \times \vee y)_p = \mu(x, p) \wedge (\mu(y, p))$, for all $x, y \in L$.

Definition 2.11:

- (i) A P-fuzzy filter is prime if $\mu(x \vee y)_p \leq S\{\mu(x, p), \mu(y, p)\}$
- (ii) A P-fuzzy ideal is prime if $\mu(x \wedge y)_p \leq S\{\mu(x, p), \mu(y, p)\}$, holds for all $x, y \in L$.

Definition 2.12:

A P-fuzzy G-modular lattice A is modular if and only if $A(x, z) \geq 0 \rightarrow x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge z$. for all x, y and $z \in X$.

Definition 2.13:

Let μ be a anti P-fuzzy G-modular lattice. If μ is distributive then

- (i) $x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$ and
- (ii) $x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z)$ for all x, y and $z \in X$.

Definition 2.14:

Let L and L' be lattices. A mapping $f: L \rightarrow L'$ is said to be lattice homomorphism if

- (ii) $f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y)$ and
- (iii) $f(xy) = f(x) \cdot f(y)$, for all $x, y \in L$.

Definition 2.15:

We say that a Anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice $M = (L, \mu_M)$ in L satisfies the imaginable property if $I_m(\mu_M)$ is subset of T .

Definition 2.16:

Let λ and μ be two anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of L . Then the sum of λ and μ are denoted by $\lambda + \mu$ and is defined as

$$(\lambda + \mu)(z, p) = \inf_{z = x + y} \{ \max \{ \lambda(x, p), \mu(y, p) \} \} \quad \text{where } x, y \in L.$$

Clearly $\lambda + \mu$ is a anti P-fuzzy G modular distributive lattice in L.

Definition 2.17:

Let λ and μ be two anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of L.

Then the ring sum of λ and μ is defined as

$$(\lambda \otimes \mu)(z, p) = \inf \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2)(z, p) / x = f^{-1}(\lambda, p), y = f^{-1}(\mu, p) \}$$

$$Z \in (\lambda \otimes \mu) \text{ for all } x, y \text{ and } z \in L$$

Characterization of Anti Q-Fuzzy G-Modular Distributive Lattices:

Throughout this paper G be a finite groups and $L = \langle L, +, \cdot \rangle$ denotes a lattice. That is of maps from L into $\langle [0, 1]; \vee, \wedge \rangle$, where $[0, 1]$ is the set of reals between 0 and 1. and

- (i) $x \vee y = \max(x, y)$, if $y \leq x$ then $\mu(y) \geq \mu(x)$ and
- (ii) $x \wedge y = \min(x, y)$, if $x \leq y$ then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$

Proposition 3.1:

Let M be a G-modular lattice and N be a anti P-fuzzy G-sub modular lattice of M has a anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice. Then M/N and N has anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice.

Proof:

Let μ be a fuzzy sub modular lattice of M. Then $V: \mu_N$ is anti P-fuzzy G-modular lattice on N.

Define $\mu: \frac{M}{N} \times P \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by

$$\mu(x + N, p) = \mu(x, p), \text{ for all } x \in G \text{ and } n \in \frac{M}{N}$$

$$(1) \quad \mu(a(x + N) + b(y + N), p) = \mu((ax + by) + N, p)$$

$$= \mu(ax + by, p)$$

$$\leq \max \{ \mu(x, p) + \mu(y, p) \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ \mu(x + N, p) + \mu(y + N, p) \}$$

$$(2) \quad \mu(g(x + N), p) = \mu(gx + N, p) = \mu(gx, p)$$

$$\leq \mu(x, p)$$

$$\leq \mu(x + N, p)$$

$$(3) \quad \mu(x \vee y)p \wedge \mu(x \wedge y)p + N = \max \{ \mu((x \vee y)p + N), \mu(x \wedge y)p + N \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ \max \{ \mu(x, p), \mu(y, p) \} + N, \{ \max \{ \mu(x, p), \mu(y, p) \} + N \} \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ \mu(x, p) + N, \mu(y, p) + N \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ \mu(x + N, p), \mu(y + N, p) \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ \mu(x, p), \mu(y, p) \}, \text{ for all } x, y \in G$$

Therefore $\frac{M}{N}$ and N are anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice.

Proposition 3.2:

Let $f: L \rightarrow L^*$ be a G-modular distributive lattice homomorphism where L and L^* are G-modular distributive lattices. If V is anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L^* , then $f^{-1}(v)$ is anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L.

Proof:

Since V is anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L^* and $f: L \rightarrow L^*$ be a G-modular lattice homomorphism. For any $a, b \in K$ and $x, y \in L$, we have

$$(1) \quad f^{-1}(V)(ax + by, p) = V(f(ax + by), p)$$

$$= V(f(ax, p) + f(by, p))$$

$$\leq V\{(f(x, p) + f(y, p))\}$$

$$\leq \max \{ V f(x, p), V f(y, p) \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ f^{-1}(V)(x, p), f^{-1}(V)(y, p) \}$$

$$(2) \quad f^{-1}(V)(gm, p) = V f(gm, p)$$

$$\leq V f(m, p)$$

$$\leq f^{-1}(V)(m, p)$$

$$(3) \quad f^{-1}(V)(x \vee y)p \wedge f^{-1}(V)(x \wedge y)p = \max \{ f^{-1}(V)((x \vee y)p), f^{-1}(V)(x \wedge y)p \}$$

$$= \max \{ V f(x \vee y, p), V f(x \wedge y, p) \}$$

$$= \max \{ V(f(x, p) + f(y, p)), V(f(x, p) \cdot f(y, p)) \}$$

(Since V is homomorphism

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \max \{ \max \{ V f(x, p), V f(y, p) \}, \{ \max \{ V f(x, p), V f(y, p) \} \} \\ &\leq \max \{ V f(x, p), V f(y, p) \} \\ &\leq \max \{ f^{-1}(v)(x, p), f^{-1}(v)(y, p) \} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $f^{-1}(V)$ is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L.

Proposition 3.3:

Let S be a t-norm. Then every imaginable anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of L is anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice.

Proof:

Let $M = (L, \mu_M)$ be an imaginable anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of L under S-norms.

Then

(i) $\mu_M(ax + by, p) \leq S \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \}$

(ii) $\mu_M(gm, p) \leq \mu_M(m, p)$,

(iii) $\mu_M(x \vee y, p) \wedge \mu_M(x \wedge y, p) \leq S \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \}$ for all $a, b \in G, x, y$ and $m \in M$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \max \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \} &= S \{ \max \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \}, \max \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \} \} \\ &\geq S \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \} \\ &\geq \max \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \} \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $\mu_M(ax + by, p) \leq S \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \}$

Therefore $M = (L, \mu_M)$ is an imaginable anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of L.

Proposition 3.4:

If L is a complete lattice, then the intersection of a family of anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice is a fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice.

Proof:

Let $\{ M_j : j \in J \}$ be a family of anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice and let $M = \bigcup M_j$

We have $\mu_M(x, p) = \sup \mu_{M_j}(x, p)$ and $\mu_M(y, p) = \sup \mu_{M_j}(y, p)$

(1) $\mu_M(ax + by, p) = \sup \mu_{M_j}(ax + by, p)$
 $\leq \sup \{ \max \{ \mu_{M_j}(x, p), \mu_{M_j}(y, p) \} \}$
 $\leq \max \{ \sup \mu_{M_j}(x, p), \sup \mu_{M_j}(y, p) \}$
 $\leq \max \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \}$

(2) $\mu_M(gx, p) = \sup \mu_{M_j}(gx, p)$
 $\leq \sup \mu_{M_j}(x, p)$
 $\leq \mu_M(x, p)$

(3) $\mu_M(x \vee y, p) \wedge \mu_M(x \wedge y, p) = \max \{ \mu_M((x \vee y, p), \mu_M(x \wedge y, p) \}$
 $= \max \{ \sup \mu_{M_j}(x \vee y, p), \sup \mu_{M_j}(x \wedge y, p) \}$
 $= \max \{ \sup \max \{ \mu_{M_j}(x, p), \mu_{M_j}(y, p) \}, \sup \max \{ \mu_{M_j}(x, p), \mu_{M_j}(y, p) \} \}$
 $\leq \max \{ \sup \mu_{M_j}(x, p), \sup \mu_{M_j}(y, p) \}$
 $\leq T \{ \mu_M(x, p), \mu_M(y, p) \}$, for all $x, y \in L$.

Therefore $\bigcup \mu_{M_j}$ is anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice.

Proposition 3.5:

Any finite dimensional G-modular distributive lattice over a sub lattice L is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice over L.

Proof:

Let $\mu: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a map and M be a finite n-dimensional anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice over L.

For all $\alpha, \beta \in L$ and $x, y \in M$

Such that $\mu^n(\alpha x, p) = \mu(n(\alpha x, p) = \mu^n(x, p)$

(1) $\mu^n(\alpha x + \beta y, p) = \mu(n(\alpha x + \beta y, p))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= n \mu (\alpha x + \beta y, p) \\
 &\leq n \mu \{ \max \{ \mu(\alpha x, p) + \mu(\beta y, p) \} \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ n \mu (\alpha x, p), n \mu (\beta y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \mu^n(\alpha x, p), \mu^n(\beta y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \mu^n(x, p), \mu^n(y, p) \} \\
 (2) \quad \mu^n (gx, p) &= \mu (n(gx, p)) \\
 &= n \mu (gx, p) \\
 &\leq n \mu (x, p) \\
 &\leq \mu^n (x, p) \\
 (3) \quad \mu^n (x \vee y)p \wedge \mu^n (x \wedge y)p &= \max \{ \mu^n ((x \vee y, p), \mu^n (x \wedge y, p) \} \\
 &= \max \{ \mu (n (x \vee y, p), \mu (n (x \wedge y, p) \} \\
 &= \max \{ n \mu \{ (x \vee y, p), n \mu (x \wedge y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ n \{ \max \{ \mu (x, p), \mu (y, p) \}, n \{ \max \{ \mu (x, p), \mu (y, p) \} \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ n \mu (x, p), n \mu (y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \mu^n(x, p), \mu^n(y, p) \}, \text{ for all } x, y \in M.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, n-dimensional anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice.

Proposition 3.6:

If M and N are anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattices over a fuzzy sub-lattice L then $L = M \otimes N$ is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L. Here \otimes is referred as a ring sum.

Proof:

Let M and N be two anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattices of μ_1 and μ_2 respectively. Then we define the ring sum of M. and N as

$$(M \otimes N) (z, p) = \inf_{z \in M \otimes N} \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (z, p) / x = f^{-1}(\mu_1, p), y = f^{-1}(\mu_2, p) \}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) (M \otimes N) (\alpha x + \beta y, p) &= (\mu_1 + \mu_2)(\alpha x + \beta y, p) \\
 &\leq \max \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (x, p), (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \inf_{z \in M \otimes N} \mu_1 (z, p), \inf_{z \in M \otimes N} \mu_2 (z, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ (M \otimes N) (z, p), M \otimes N (z, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ (M \otimes N) (x, p), M \otimes N (y, p) \} \\
 (2) (M \otimes N) (gz, p) &= (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (gz, p) \\
 &\leq (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (z, p) \\
 &\leq \inf \{ \mu_1 + \mu_2 \} (z, p) \\
 &\quad z \in M \otimes N \\
 &\leq (M \otimes N) (z, p) \tag{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (M \otimes N)(x \vee y)p \wedge (M \otimes N)(x \wedge y)p &= \max \{ (M \otimes N) (x \vee y, p), (M \otimes N)(x \wedge y, p) \} \\
 &= \max \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (x \vee y, p), (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (x \wedge y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \max \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (x, p), (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (y, p) \}, \max \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (x, p), (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (y, p) \} \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (x, p), (\mu_1 + \mu_2) (y, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ \inf_{z \in M \otimes N} \mu_1 (z, p), \inf_{z \in M \otimes N} \mu_2 (z, p) \} \\
 &\leq \max \{ (M \otimes N) (x, p), M \otimes N (y, p) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $M \otimes N$ is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattices.

Proposition 3.7:

Let M be a G-modular distributive lattices over a sub lattice L and $M = \sum_{i=1}^n M_i$, where M_i 's are G sub modular distributive lattice of M. If V_i are anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of M_i , then $V: M \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice in L.

Proof:

Since V_i is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on M_i for every $x, y \in M_i$; $g \in L$ and $\alpha, \beta \in L$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad V(\alpha x + \beta y, p) &= V(\sum(\alpha M_i + \beta M_i', p)) \\
 &= \Lambda(V_i(\alpha M_i + \beta M_i', p)), \text{ where } i = 1, 2 \dots n. \\
 &= V_j(\alpha M_j + \beta M_j', p), \text{ for some } j \\
 &\leq \max(V_j(M_j, p), V_j(M_j', p)) \\
 &\leq \max(V(x, p), V(y, p)) \\
 (2) \quad V(gx, p) &= V(\sum gM_i, p) \\
 &= \Lambda(V_i(gM_i, p), \text{ where } i = 1, 2 \dots n. \\
 &= V_j(gM_j, p), \text{ for some } j \\
 &\leq V_j(M_j, p) \\
 &\leq V(x, p) \\
 (3) \quad V(x \vee y)p \wedge V(x \wedge y)p &= \max\{V((x \vee y), p), V(x \wedge y, p)\} \\
 &= \max\{V\sum(x \vee y, p)M_i, V\sum(x \wedge y, p)M_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots n \\
 &= \max\{V(x \vee y, p)M_i, V(x \wedge y, p)M_i\} \\
 &\leq \max\{\max\{V(x, p), V(y, p)\}M_i, \{\max\{V(x, p), V(y, p)\}M_i\} \max\{V(x, p)M_i, V(y, p)M_i\}\} \\
 &\leq \max\{V_i M_j, V_j M_j'\}, \text{ for some } j. \\
 &\leq \max\{V(x, p), V(y, p)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore V is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L .

Proposition 3.8:

Let λ and μ be anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattices of L , Then $\lambda + \mu$ is the smallest anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice of L .

Proof:

For any $x, y, h, f \in L$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) \quad \max\{(\lambda + \mu)p x, (\lambda + \mu)p y\} &= \max\{\inf \max\{(\lambda(a,p), \mu(b,p))\}, \\
 &\quad x = a + b \\
 &\quad \inf \max\{(\lambda(c,p), \mu(d,p))\} \\
 &\quad y = c + d \\
 &= \max\{\inf(\max\{(\lambda(a,p), \mu(b,p)), \max\{(\lambda(c,p), \mu(d,p))\}) \\
 &\quad x = a + b \\
 &\quad y = c + d \\
 &= \max\{\inf \max\{(\lambda(a,p), \mu(b,p), \lambda(c,p), \mu(d,p))\} \\
 &\quad x = a + b \\
 &\quad y = c + d \\
 &\geq \max\{\inf \max\{(\lambda(a+(b-c-b),p), \mu(b+(c-d-c),p))\} \\
 &\quad x = a + b \\
 &\quad y = c + d \\
 &\geq \max\{\inf \max\{(\lambda(h,p), \mu(f,p))\} \\
 &\quad x + y \\
 &\quad = h + f \\
 &\geq (\lambda + \mu)p(x + y)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $(\lambda + \mu)(x + y) \leq S\{(\lambda + \mu)p(x), (\lambda + \mu)p(y)\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2) \quad (\lambda + \mu)(gx, p) &= \inf \max\{(\lambda(a,p), \mu(b,p))\} \\
 &\quad x = a + b \\
 &= \inf \max\{(\lambda(a,p), \mu(b,p))\} \\
 &\quad g_x = g_a + g_b \\
 &\leq \inf \max\{(\lambda(A,p), \mu(B,p))\} \\
 &\quad X = G_A + G_B \\
 &\leq (\lambda + \mu)(x, p)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (3) \quad (\lambda + \mu)(x \vee y)p \wedge (\lambda + \mu)(x \wedge y)p &= \max\{(\lambda + \mu)(x \vee y)p, (\lambda + \mu)(x \wedge y)p\} \\
 &= S\{\max\{(\lambda + \mu)(x,p), (\lambda + \mu)(y,p)\}, \\
 &\quad \max\{(\lambda + \mu)(x,p), (\lambda + \mu)(y,p)\}\} \\
 &= S\{\max\{\inf \max\{\lambda(x,p), \mu(x,p) \\
 &\quad x = a + b \\
 &\quad \inf \max\{\lambda(y,p), \mu(y,p)\}, \\
 &\quad y = c + d \\
 &= \max\{\inf \max\{\lambda(x,p), \mu(x,p)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & x = a + b \\
 & \inf \max \{ \lambda(y,q), \mu(y,q) \} \\
 & y = c + d \\
 & \leq S \{ \inf \max \{ \lambda(y,p), \mu(y,p) \}, \\
 & y = c + d \\
 & \inf \max \{ \lambda(x,p), \mu(x,p) \} \\
 & x = a + b \\
 & \leq S \{ \inf \max \{ \lambda(x,p), \mu(x,p) \}, \\
 & x = a + b \\
 & \inf \max \{ \lambda(y,p), \mu(y,p) \} \\
 & y = c + d \\
 & \leq S \{ (\lambda + \mu)(x,p), (\lambda + \mu)(y,p) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $(\lambda + \mu)(x \vee y)_p \wedge (\lambda + \mu)(x \wedge y)_p \leq S \{ (\lambda + \mu)(x,p), (\lambda + \mu)(y,p) \}$

Hence $(\lambda + \mu)$ is anti P- fuzzy G-modular distributive lattice on L.

Conclusions:

I. Jahan [2008] introduce the concept of modularity of Ajmal [1995] for the lattices of fuzzy ideals of a ring. In this paper, we study the characterization of anti P-fuzzy G-modular distributive lattices. One can obtain the similar results in soft modules and soft lattices by using a suitable mathematical tool.

References:

1. N. Ajmal, The “Lattice of fuzzy normal sub groups is modular”, Inform. Sci. 83 (1995), pp. 199-209.
2. N. Ajmal, K.V. Thomas, “A complete study of the lattices of fuzzy congruences and fuzzy normal sub groups, Inform. Sci. 82 (1995), pp. 198-218.
3. S-Z. Bai, “Pre-semi compact L-sub sets in fuzzy lattices”. International Journal of fuzzy systems, Vol.12, No.1, pp.59-65, 2010.
4. Y.Bo and Wu. Wangning, “Fuzzy ideals on a distributive lattice”, Fuzzy sets and systems. Vol. 81 (1996), pp.383 – 393.
5. S.K. Bhambri, Pratibha Kumar, “Lattice of fuzzy sub modules”, International mathematical forum, 4 (2009) No.13, pp.653-659.
6. P. Das, “Fuzzy groups and level sub groups”, J. Math. Anal. Appl., Vol.85 (1981), pp.264-269.
7. Golan. J.S., “Making Modules fuzzy”, Fuzzy sets and systems, 32 (1989), pp.91-94.
8. I. Jahan, “Modularity of Ajmal for the lattices of fuzzy ideals of a ring”, Iranian Journal of fuzzy systems, Vol.5, No.2 (2008), pp. 71 – 78.
9. R. Kumar, “Non distributivity of the lattice of fuzzy ideals of a ring R”, Fuzzy sets and systems, 97 (1998), pp.393-394.
10. W.J. Liu, “Fuzzy invariant sub groups and fuzzy ideals, “Fuzzy sets and systems, Vo.8 (1982), pp.133-139.
11. Majumdar, Sultana, “The lattice of fuzzy ideals of a ring R”, Fuzzy sets and systems, 81 (1996), pp.271-273.
12. Pan, Fu-zheng, “Fuzzy finitely generated modules”, Fuzzy sets and systems, 21 (1987), pp. 105-113.
13. A. Rosenfeld, “Fuzzy groups”, J. Maths. Anal. Appl. Vol.35 (1971), pp.512-517.
14. L.A. Zadeh, “Fuzzy sets”, Inform. Control. Vo.8 (1965), pp.338-353.
15. Q. Zhang, Meng, “On the lattice of fuzzy ideals of a ring”, Fuzzy sets and systems, 112 (2000) pp. 349-353.